

Charging of an AC three-phase Electric Vehicle: Power Quality Analysis up to 150 kHz

Giovanni Artale
University of Palermo
Department of Engineering
Palermo, Italy
giovanni.artale@unipa.it

Valentina Cosentino
University of Palermo
Department of Engineering
Palermo, Italy
valentina.cosentino@unipa.it

Dario Costanzo
Università degli Studi della Campania
"Luigi Vanvitelli"
Aversa (CE), Italy
dario.costanzo@studenti.unicampania.it

Antonio Delle Femine
Università degli Studi della Campania
"Luigi Vanvitelli"
Aversa (CE), Italy
antonio.dellefemine@unicampania.it

Dario Di Cara
National Research Council
Institute of Marine Engineering
Palermo, Italy
dario.dicara@cnr.it

Vito Ditta
National Research Council
Institute of Marine Engineering
Palermo, Italy
vito.ditta@cnr.it

Daniele Gallo
Università degli Studi della Campania
"Luigi Vanvitelli"
Aversa (CE), Italy
daniele.gallo@unicampania.it

Mario Luiso
Università degli Studi della Campania
"Luigi Vanvitelli"
Aversa (CE), Italy
mario.luiso@unicampania.it

Nicola Panzavecchia
National Research Council
Institute of Marine Engineering
Palermo, Italy
nicola.panzavecchia@cnr.it

Abstract—The escalating adoption of electric vehicles (EVs), fueled by heightened environmental awareness and advancements in battery technology, is driving a significant demand for expanded charging infrastructure, encompassing residential solutions, public charging stations with AC and DC capabilities, and high-power fast charging stations (HPFCS). While the transition to EVs promises substantial benefits in terms of reduced greenhouse gas emissions and improved energy efficiency, the widespread integration of EV charging introduces novel challenges for the electrical power grid, notably concerning Power Quality (PQ). This paper presents experimental results coming from a field measurement campaign, performed with high bandwidth instrumentation and high sample frequency. The acquired data are suitable for harmonic analysis up to 150 kHz and for investigating the so-called supraharmmonic emissions originating from EV chargers and their consequential impact on the grid. These investigations are conducted in accordance with international standards that delineate methodologies for power quality assessment and specify requirements for the design and operation of electric vehicle charging systems, aiming to ensure safety, interoperability, and the minimization of adverse grid effects. The final aim is to provide a case study analysis of the potential impact of EVs charging stations on the ac power grid, also highlighting the main measurement issues related to PQ assessment for such systems.

Index Terms—e-Mobility, Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment, Battery Electric Vehicle, field measurement, power measurement, energy measurement, Supraharmmonic, high frequency emissions.

I. INTRODUCTION

The global shift towards electrification of transportation, propelled by growing environmental awareness and advance-

ments in battery technology, has led to a significant increase in the adoption of electric vehicles (EVs) across various sectors. This surge in EV ownership necessitates a corresponding development and expansion of the charging infrastructure, encompassing residential charging solutions, public EV charging stations (EVCS) with AC and DC options, and high-power fast charging stations (HPFCS) designed for rapid recharging [1]–[3]. While the transition to EVs offers substantial benefits in terms of reduced greenhouse gas emissions and enhanced energy efficiency, the widespread integration of EV charging presents new challenges to the electrical power grid, particularly concerning Power Quality (PQ).

The process of charging electric vehicles relies heavily on power electronic converters (PECs), which are integrated either within the vehicle (on-board charger) or as part of the charging station (off-board charger) [4]. These converters frequently employ switching technologies such as active Power Factor Correction (PFC) circuits and Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) techniques to regulate the charging process and improve efficiency [5], [6]. However, the operation of these power electronic devices introduces non-linear loads to the electrical grid. Consequently, EV charging can generate a spectrum of harmonic currents and voltages, extending beyond the fundamental frequency (typically 50 Hz or 60 Hz) into the tens of kilohertz range, specifically within the domain of supraharmonics (2–150 kHz) [7], [8] and potentially overlapping with the CISPR Band A (9–150 kHz). Several power quality issues are commonly associated with EV charging:

- Harmonic Distortion: Older EV charger models, in particular, have been observed to generate significant current harmonics, leading to a considerable Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) [3]. These harmonics can cause overheating in transformers and other electrical equipment, interfere with the operation of sensitive electronic devices, and increase energy losses in the distribution network [1].
- Supraharmonic Emissions: The switching frequencies of PECs within EV chargers often fall within the 2 kHz to 150 kHz range, resulting in unintentional emissions in the supraharmonic spectrum [6], [7]. These emissions can propagate through the low-voltage grid and potentially interfere with other grid-connected devices, leading to malfunctions, audible noise, and increased heating. Moreover, supraharmonics can also disrupt the functionality of Power Line Communication (PLC) systems, which are increasingly utilized for smart grid applications such as automated meter reading.
- Voltage Fluctuations and Flicker: The operation of large-scale fast-charging stations, which draw significant amounts of power in relatively short periods, can cause voltage dips and fluctuations in the distribution network. These voltage variations can lead to noticeable light flicker and may affect the performance of other connected loads [9].

Understanding and mitigating these PQ issues associated with AC three-phase EV charging is crucial for ensuring the reliable and efficient operation of both the electrical grid and the increasing number of electric vehicles connected to it. This work investigates PQ issues related to the electric vehicle charging process, with a focus on high-frequency emissions.

II. STATE OF THE ART

The impact of electric vehicle charging on PQ has been a subject of increasing investigation in scientific literature. Early studies focused primarily on the low-order harmonic distortion (below 2 kHz) caused by EV battery chargers. Research conducted in the 1990s highlighted the significant harmonic generation by older charger technologies, with THD in current ranging from 20% to over 112% [3]. However, later studies indicated that newer commercially available vehicles implement more sophisticated chargers that generate significantly lower current harmonics, with THD potentially ranging from 3.72% to 7.18% in some cases. Computer simulations have also suggested that when a large number of chargers operate simultaneously, harmonic cancellation can occur, potentially reducing the cumulative THD.

More recent scientific literature has increasingly focused on the impact of EV charging on supraharmonics, the frequency range between 2 kHz and 150 kHz [6]. Studies have investigated the emission characteristics of various devices, including EV chargers, in this higher frequency range and their interaction with the low-voltage grid [7]. These studies emphasize that modern PECs, commonly used in EV chargers for active power factor correction, are primary sources of supraharmonic emissions due to their switching frequencies.

Research has analyzed the supraharmonic current emissions of different types of Battery Electric Vehicles (BEVs) during their charging cycles, both under laboratory conditions and in real low-voltage grids [6]. The superposition of supraharmonic emissions from multiple simultaneously charging EVs and the influence of grid impedance have also been explored through modeling and measurements. The impact of fast charging stations on PQ in distribution systems, considering harmonics, supraharmonics, and voltage fluctuation, has also been assessed probabilistically using methods like Monte Carlo simulations. These analyses often involve measuring power demand and harmonic distortion at fast charging stations with different vehicle types and chargers from various manufacturers to quantify their impact on the power system [9].

In parallel to the scientific literature, several international standards provide guidelines and requirements related to PQ and EVs charging systems. IEC 61000-3-2 [5] regulates the harmonic emission of electronic devices in the low-frequency range up to 2.5 kHz [4].

For PQ measurement in general, IEC 61000-4-30 [10] specifies methods for measuring and interpreting power quality parameters, including voltage, current, frequency, and harmonics. This standard also provides considerations for measurement methods of conducted voltage emissions in the 2 kHz to 150 kHz range in its Annex C. The measurement of harmonic currents and voltages is further detailed in IEC 61000-4-7 [11]. For EVs charging systems specifically, IEC 61851-1 [12] outlines the general requirements for conductive charging, including definitions of charging modes, safety requirements, and interface specifications.

While not explicitly setting limits on harmonic emissions, this standard emphasizes the need to design charging systems to limit the introduction of harmonic and non-sinusoidal currents that could negatively affect residual current devices or other equipment. The IEC 62196 series of standards [13] focuses on the dimensional compatibility and interchangeability requirements for plugs, socket-outlets, vehicle connectors, and vehicle inlets used in conductive charging. These standards ensure the safe and interoperable physical connection between the EV and the charging infrastructure for both AC (IEC 62196-2) and DC (IEC 62196-3, IEC TS 62196-3-1) charging. Furthermore, the ISO 15118 [14], [15] series defines the communication protocol between the EV and the Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment (EVSE), which indirectly supports power quality management through features like controlled charging and potential future integration of vehicle-to-grid functionalities [14].

III. MEASUREMENT CAMPAIGN

A. Site Description

The vehicle under test was connected to a three-phase charging station with a nominal power of 22 kW that belongs to a cluster of charging stations. These are located within a resort in Balestrate, near to Palermo, Italy, in a remote area, with only a few neighboring villas. The resort is connected to the low voltage network, where both the charging stations

and all resort facilities including accommodations, reception, kitchens, services for the swimming pools, SPA, the heating and cooling system, etc. Different photovoltaic plants are installed on the roof of the buildings. They have a total power of 80 kW peak. The tests were carried out in the winter period, with a reduced tourist flux. Therefore, only the electric vehicle under test and a few loads were connected to the secondary substation, since several services were temporarily turned off. Furthermore, the weather conditions did not allow any emissions from the photovoltaic systems. The measured disturbances can therefore be attributed to the charging of the vehicle.

B. Measurement Setup

The measurement setup is based on a National Instruments (NI) PCI eXtension for Instrumentation (PXI) system. It has two Data Acquisition boards (DAQs) NI PXIe-6124 (± 10 V, 16 bit, 4 MHz, 4 synchronous channels) for the acquisition of six electrical quantities, three voltages and three currents. Three voltage sensors LEM CV3-1000 (± 1000 V, 500 kHz) [16] and three current sensors Pearson Current Monitor 411 (50 A, 20 MHz) [17] are used.

IV. MEASUREMENT RESULTS

Acquired voltage and current waveforms are reported in Fig.1 and Fig.2 (phase 1). The rms values for voltage and current are 240.61 V and 16.12 A, respectively. Time domain waveforms show a visible distortion on the current in correspondence to zero crossings and peaks zones. Phase 1 instantaneous power on the same time interval has been calculated and it is depicted in Fig.3. Measured phase 1 active power is 3875.48 W.

The frequency domain analysis was performed by dividing the frequency spectra into three ranges: from 0 to 2 kHz, from 2 up to 9 kHz and from 9 to 150 kHz. The harmonic analyses of phase 1 measured voltage are reported in Figs. 4, 5, and 6 for the three frequency ranges 0 to 2 kHz, 2 kHz to 9 kHz and 9 kHz to 150 kHz, respectively. The low-frequency spectrum (0-2 kHz) shows the fundamental component at 50 Hz and different harmonics; the 250 Hz harmonic has the highest amplitude. Many disturbances can be detected in the 2 - 9 kHz range as well. For this frequency range, the figure 5 shows the results of the 200 Hz grouping process applied to the calculated DFT, as stated by IEC 61000-4-7. In the highest frequency range (see 6), the grouping process uses bands of 2 kHz, according to IEC 61000-4-7. In this frequency range, the highest disturbances can be easily detected around 19 kHz and 64 kHz. The harmonic analyses of phase 1 measured current are reported in Figs. 7, 8 and 9 for the same three frequency ranges (0 to 2 kHz, 2 kHz to 9 kHz and 9 kHz to 150 kHz, respectively). Comparing the measured spectra of current and voltage, similar behavior is observed for the lowest frequency range, while in the higher frequency ranges the distortion profile is different. In fact, the disturbances on the current decrease with frequency, in the range 2-9 kHz; significant harmonic groups are also observed in the highest

Fig. 1. Measured Voltage on phase 1

Fig. 2. Measured Current on phase 1

frequency range, around 11 kHz, 19 kHz, 25 kHz, 35 Hz and 64 kHz.

Fig. 3. Instantaneous power on phase 1

Fig. 4. Harmonic Analysis of Voltage 0-2 kHz

Fig. 6. Harmonic Analysis of Voltage 9-150 kHz

Fig. 5. Harmonic Analysis of Voltage 2-9 kHz

Fig. 7. Harmonic Analysis of Current 0-2 kHz

CONCLUSIONS

This paper has presented a case-study analysis of the impact of EV charging stations on the ac power grid, based on on-field measurements. Voltage and current spectra have been analyzed, in the frequency range up to 150 kHz, showing that significant harmonic components are present in the whole considered frequency range, due to the chargers' power electronic converters. This poses attention to some PQ issues related to in the presence of such systems, such as those related to disturbances injection on the grid, worsening of energy efficiency and possible interferences with power line communication systems. In this framework, current state of PQ analysis pertaining to EVs chargers encompasses a growing body of scientific literature dedicated to investigating harmonic and, with increasing emphasis, supraharmonic emissions from electric vehicle chargers and their ramifications for the elec-

trical network. These studies are complemented by a set of international standards that establish frameworks for PQ measurement and define specifications for the design and operation of EVs charging systems, with the dual objectives of ensuring safety and interoperability while mitigating potential negative impacts on the power grid. In parallel with this, the presence of the aforesaid disturbances poses further measurement issues concerning proper instrumentation for PQ levels and energy efficiency assessment. In fact in the study herein presented, measurement data were collected with high-accuracy instrumentation; however, in the perspective of increasing diffusion of EV chargers (as well as of other PECs-based systems, such as those of distributed generation and storage systems), it is important to specify the metrological requirements for on-field instrumentation (even low-cost), capable to perform measurements with the desired accuracy.

Fig. 8. Harmonic Analysis of Current 2-9 kHz

Fig. 9. Harmonic Analysis of Current 9-150 kHz

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The activities presented here were developed in the framework of the project 23IND06 Met4EVCS funded by the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States. This work was supported in part by research project 2022FLWXTA entitled "Electrical Measurements and Instrumentation for the Evaluation of E-mobility Impact on Islands Power Systems and Microgrids" (EMIIslands) CUP B53D23002590006, and by research project P2022XL9NX entitled "Measurement-based techniques for renewable energy systems and their integration in the case

of Small Islands" (MERSIS) CUP B53D23024150001, both funded by the Next Generation EU" - PNRR M4 - C2 - investment 1.1: Fondo per il Programma Nazionale di Ricerca e Progetti di Rilevante Interesse Nazionale (PRIN). The authors wish to thank Petruso Resort for the availability of the electric vehicle, the charging station and the technical support for measurement and data collection.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Fitrianto, M. C. Fatah, and I. G. Mulyana K., "The effect of public electric vehicle charging station on the harmonic and electrifying lifestyle improvement in bandung," in *2023 International Conference on Technology and Policy in Energy and Electric Power (ICT-PEP)*, 2023, pp. 150–155.
- [2] M. Parchomiuk, A. Moradewicz, and H. Gawiński, "An overview of electric vehicles fast charging infrastructure," in *2019 Progress in Applied Electrical Engineering (PAEE)*, 2019, pp. 1–5.
- [3] S. Berisha, G. Karady, R. Ahmad, R. Hobbs, and D. Karner, "Current harmonics generated by electric vehicle battery chargers," in *Proceedings of International Conference on Power Electronics, Drives and Energy Systems for Industrial Growth*, vol. 1, 1996, pp. 584–589 vol.1.
- [4] A. J. Collin, S. Z. Djokic, H. F. Thomas, and J. Meyer, "Modelling of electric vehicle chargers for power system analysis," in *11th International Conference on Electrical Power Quality and Utilisation*, 2011, pp. 1–6.
- [5] International Electrotechnical Commission. (2018) IEC 61000-3-2: Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) - Part 3-2: Limits - Limits for harmonic current emissions.
- [6] S. Schöttke, J. Meyer, P. Schegner, and S. Bachmann, "Emission in the frequency range of 2 khz to 150 khz caused by electrical vehicle charging," in *2014 International Symposium on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, 2014, pp. 620–625.
- [7] C. Waniek, T. Wohlfahrt, J. M. Myrzik, J. Meyer, M. Klatt, and P. Schegner, "Supraharmonics: Root causes and interactions between multiple devices and the low voltage grid," in *2017 IEEE PES Innovative Smart Grid Technologies Conference Europe (ISGT-Europe)*, 2017, pp. 1–6.
- [8] A. Mariscotti, "Harmonic and supraharmonic emissions of plug-in electric vehicle chargers," *Smart Cities*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 496–521, 2022.
- [9] B. Basta and W. G. Morsi, "Probabilistic assessment of the impact of integrating large-scale high-power fast charging stations on the power quality in the distribution systems," in *2020 IEEE Electric Power and Energy Conference (EPEC)*, 2020, pp. 1–6.
- [10] International Electrotechnical Commission, "IEC 61000-4-30: Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) - Part 4-30: Testing and measurement techniques - Power quality measurement methods," 2015.
- [11] —, "IEC 61000-4-7: Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) - Part 4-7: Testing and measurement techniques - General guide on harmonics and interharmonics measurements and instrumentation, for power supply systems and equipment connected thereto," 2002.
- [12] IEC. (2010) Iec 61851-1 ed2.0: Electric vehicle conductive charging system - part 1: General requirements.
- [13] International Electrotechnical Commission, "IEC 62196: Plugs, socket-outlets, vehicle connectors and vehicle inlets - Conductive charging of electric vehicles," 2022.
- [14] ISO/IEC. (2012) Iso/iec dis 15118-2: Road vehicles - vehicle to grid communication interface - part 2: Network and application protocol requirements.
- [15] —. (2012) Iso/iec dis 15118-3: Road vehicles - vehicle to grid communication interface - part 3: Physical and data link layer requirements.
- [16] (2025) Lem cv 3-1000. [Online]. Available: <https://www.lem.com/en/product-list/cv-31000>
- [17] (2025) Pearson current monitor model 411. [Online]. Available: <https://pearsonelectronics.com/pdf/411.pdf>